

Impact of Visionary Leadership on Pro-Social Motivation and Emotional Exhaustion

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Article History:	ABSTRACT
Received: 27 Apr, 2021	Purpose: The study's goal is to investigate the impact of visionary leadership on pro-social motivation and emotional exhaustion, which will be useful for organizations in the future; it also proves the value of visionary leadership. Making a strategy for staff to reduce emotional exhaustion will be beneficial. It stated that visionary leadership is linked to pro-social motivation in a good way.
Revised: 06 Dec, 2021	Design and Methodology: As a sample of 350 respondents from different Pakistani banks from Rawalpindi and Islamabad. The instrument of data collection is questionnaire, which consist of 32 items (questions). There are three parts of questionnaire, one part for each variable. There are 6 items for visionary leadership, 8 items for pro-social motivation, 9 items for emotional exhaustion, and 9 items for demographic data respectively.
Accepted: 26 Dec, 2021	Findings: Results of regression analysis for first hypothesis revealed that there is a significantly positive relationship between visionary leadership and pro-social motivation. Likewise, the results of regression analysis for second hypothesis revealed that there is a significantly negative relationship between visionary leadership and emotional exhaustion.
	Implications: The findings of the study implicate that the visionary leadership in an organization promotes the efficiency. The leadership qualities can be enhanced by running leadership development programs.
	Keywords: Visionary Leadership, Pro-social, Emotional Exhaustion, Regression Analysis

1. Introduction

Employees are the essential part of any organization and it is important to care about their emotions. Organizations are introducing several options for leadership to manage emotions of employees, also looking for social motivational cultures in organizations. Emotional exhaustion is a common issue, which have been observed from past few decades (Ghalandari et al., 2012; Haque & Aslam, 2011; Measure et al., 2006; Qureshi & Sajjad, 2015; Wigert & Agrawal, 2018). Pendell (2018) found 44% of employees sometimes feel burnout while 23% always feel burnout, following

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Gallup study. Mostly emotional exhaustion is fundamental to burnout occurrence (Maslach et al., 2001). It is important for organizations to avoid emotional exhaustion at workplace and it became dominant understanding in literature (Halbesleben & Demerouti, 2005; Kristensen et al., 2005; Measure et al., 2006). Particularly, banking sector deserves analysis for the increase in their stress and emotional exhaustion. It could be caused by change in organizational preferences and practices, especially, restructuring of processes after global financial crisis. Mostly bankers get stress, substantially from workplace the time they restrain in their bank.

So, it is hard for individual banker to overcome stress and burnout in such conditions, majorly caused by his or her career. Whenever, an individual gets fail to handle stress in several circumstances in his or her career, its consequences lead to emotional exhaustion. International Labour Organization (2016) reported that disturbing matters for employees in banking and financial sector; included problem with the study of workplace efficiency, increase in the cases of violence and stress, excessive work load, time pressure, contradictory roles, and difficulties in customer relationship (Giga & Hoel, 2003) and another study by Wigert & Agrawal (2018) determined the causes of emotional exhaustion. Among all these causes from both studies, majority causes are related to leadership of the management. It is hard for them to manage burden to perform, events, financial instruments, relations, organizational environment of banks, advancement opportunities (Khattak et al., 2011; Near & Smith, 1983).

Resultantly, all these factors or constraints are demonstrating egocentric intentions of bankers which mean absence of pro-social motivation, for instance opportunities for advancement and target based tasks are unintentionally creating competition among particular employees of bank. It turns to be very hard to tackle burden of workload, emotional imbalance, time pressure, and conflicting roles without pro-social motivation of other colleagues. To answer the question “why do employees go above and beyond to the job they are responsible to keep up their performance efficiently?” Scholars related to organizational studies have started to climax the significance of pro-social motivation to answer this question. Pro-social motivation means the aspiration to help others. Pro-social motivation enables the system to enrich the persistency of performance, efficiency and productivity by allowing commitment to moral principle, cause, capable to accept and consume the negative feedback, and dedicated to those who get advantage from one’s effort (Grant, 2007; Meglino & Korsgaard, 2004; Shamir, 1990; Thompson & Bunderson, 2014).

Therefore, leadership styles and their influences to realize shared objectives are crucial to have in management skills. Since, leaders can change and facilitate all the efforts to improve organizational performance (Yukl, 2012). Leadership skills are needed in organizations i.e. they have introduced policies and standards to create or improve leadership skills as human resource development program (Corcoran, 1995; Mendez-Morse, 1992). Vision is known as, a picture of future that what will be but not yet and it explains the purpose of decision making in present. In organizations, it is very important for management to have visionary abilities, where they can make appropriate decision making. That’s why, visionary leadership is necessary to achieve future goals.

People get inspired from leader and get empowered to work, eventually they find a clear direction. Practitioners and researchers have worked a lot to identify leadership characteristics that enhance organizational performance (Sharma, 2013; Vroom & Jago, 2007; Yukl, 2012). Zhou et al. (2018) proposed that there is a positive association between employee creativity and visionary leadership. So, considering the prior researches, which mentioned above are demonstrating that visionary leadership would be positively related to pro-social motivation and negatively related to emotional exhaustion. In this study we have examined the impact of the visionary leadership on pro-social motivation and emotional exhaustion. Now, the results should show the positive impact of visionary leadership on pro-social motivation and negative impact on the emotional exhaustion.

Here, two objectives for this study, given as follow:

- To examine that visionary leadership positively effect the pro-social motivation
- To examine that visionary leadership negatively effect the emotional exhaustion

2. Literature Review

Visionary leadership, pro-social motivation, and emotional exhaustion have been the topics of the discussion in literature, separately and collectively. Every variable one by one and explore that what topic were under discussion related our model. Firstly, elaborate visionary leadership, next pro-social motivation, and then emotional exhaustion.

2.1 Visionary Leadership

Vision is known as, a picture of future that what will happen but has not occurred yet, and it explains the purpose of decision making in present. It is defined as “established goals and objectives for individual and group action, which define not what we are but rather what we seek to be or do” (Dhammika, 2014). In organizations, it is very important for management to have visionary abilities, where they can make appropriate decision making. That’s why, Visionary leadership is necessary to achieve future goals. People get inspired from leader and get empowered to work, eventually they find a clear direction. Visionary leader become able to observe the signs of change, complications, and obvious opportunities and also have distinct event and refined trend, as other people have all that, but only visionary leaders can feel them before most of others. Another ability of visionary leaders is to take risk on their anticipations.

Visionary leaders calculate future risk with the information they glean to insight about the upcoming. If consider two dimensions of amount of risks we usually face, one risks type is cost darer and other risk type is hard to manage because they vary from situation to situation or decision to decision. We can’t stop to make decisions to avoid risk, because risk is the part of life, while, doing nothing can be a greater risk. It is the important ability of visionary leader to communication its vision properly to employees i.e. they can find a right direction to work. Therefore, leadership

styles and their influences to realize shared objectives are crucial to have in management skills. Because, leaders can change and facilitate all the efforts to improve organizational performance (Yukl, 2012).

From past two decades, numerous dominant theories have raised to investigate the leadership style and its effects on organizational performance, as Conger & Kanungo (1994) revealed the charismatic leadership theories, Edema & A (2018) and Bass & Riggio (1998) have also worked on different leadership styles. A study conducted by (Cheema et al., 2015) have examined the effect of visionary leadership and employee engagement on the employee satisfaction and the customers satisfaction, where visionary leadership was split into vision guiding and emotional commitment. The results revealed that visionary leadership (vision guiding and emotional commitment) and employee engagement are significantly related to the employees' satisfaction and customers' satisfaction. Further, outcomes explained that emotional commitment, which was the part of visionary leadership, has significant relationship with employees and customers' satisfaction.

The ability of a person to perceive and predict the future, able to face upcoming consequences, having clearly anticipated decisions. Successful leaders more accentuate on vision (Çınar & Kaban, 2012) and most of the exemplary leaders are defined by inspirational and visionary abilities of their followers (Bass & Riggio, 1998; Conger & Kanungo, 1994). It has demonstrated the strong effect of visionary leadership on organizational level, group level and individual level of analysis, by Meta-analyses and empirical researches. Bunnoiko & Atthirawong (2017) have investigated that influential factors, which are influencing the visionary leadership, and seek them from the perspective of scholars and related studies (Howell & Frost, 1989; Manning & Robertson, 2002). It revealed the following influential factors, given as follow:

- Organizational Climate
- Communication
- Emotional Intelligence
- Creativity, and
- Traits

Visionary leader always knows that how to make strategy and the appropriate time to apply it in the organization management that can change the company's failure into future success (Finkelstein & Hambrick, 1996). It is essential for visionary leaders to point out the future growths and improvements by creating and communicating future vision for the organization (Robbins, Judge, & Hasham, 2003). Visionary leaders have ability to empower the followers and allow them to participate in the shared vision, which is linked with organizational needs and future goals and objectives. Mostly, the visionary leaders have three following steps:

1. Sharing of Vision – creating effective vision, linked with the followers' assessment and ultimate results which brings emphasis on progress.

2. Imagination of vision to link and communicate to the followers with that vision, and visionary leader must effectively communicate the changes in vision and empower the followers to participate in the decision of leader and make them feel responsible.

3. In case of any change expected in organization, visionary leader must be capable of identify sub-vision and ensure the acceptance of vision by boosting confidence of followers and enhancement in the efficiency of visionary leadership.

2.2 Pro-social Motivation

With the recognition of different scholars, pro-social behavior in the organization has been the topic of interest and defined as, someone perform something with the intention of helping others, or supporting the welfare of others (Javeed et al., 2019). Hu & Liden (2012) considered the pro-social motivation as the team motivation, which mean a little devotion has been used for the motivation in team. They proposed the model in which they linked the team pro-social motivation to the team effectiveness and team process as a mediating variable. It is defined as the aspiration to promote and protect the welfare of others and it is different from altruism (Grant & Berg, 2012). Motivation means reason to act, and pro-social means the intention to benefit others (Oxford English Dictionary, 2014). In simple word, it is desire or willingness to help other people (Batson, 1987; Grant, 2007). For the better understanding of concept, it is suitable to position pro-social motivation in the basic background of motivation. And, many psychologists and researchers, including Vallerand (1997), discussed that there are three levels of motivation generalization, given as follow:

- Global Motivation
- Contextual Motivation, and
- Situational Motivation

Global motivation – concentrates toward the employee's orientation to specific goals and actions, across situation and time. This orientation is relatively stable dispositional orientation of employees.

Contextual motivation – concentrates on the motivation of employees to the particular domain of behavior, which is moderate across the situation and time.

Situational motivation – concentrates on highly variable behavior of employee's motivation in the specific time and situation.

Another term, related to pro-social motivation, also has been circulated in literature called 'public service motivation' which is associated as common altruistic motivation to help for the welfare of the community, a state or nation, or humankind (Rainey & Steinbauer, 1999). The unique work value in the public administrative organization, and different motivations mostly observed in the officials of public organizations relative to the officials in private sector are called public service motivation (Perry et al., 2010). Job design has also been studied with pro-social differences, as the job design stimulates the intentions to make pro-social differences and its effect on the actions and

identities of employees. Pro-social motivation means the aspiration to help others. Pro-social motivation enables the system to enrich the persistency of performance, efficiency and productivity by allowing commitment to moral principle, cause, capable to accept and consume the negative feedback, and dedicated to those who get advantage from one's effort (Grant, 2007; Meglino & Korsgaard, 2004; Shamir, 1990; Thompson & Bunderson, 2014).

It is important for any organization to enhance the performance and productivity of employees and some scholars thought that pro-social motivation is a significant factor among others. Grant (2008) has drawn a theory which claimed that pro-social motivation is useful to achieve persistency, performance, and productivity, when it is accompanied with intrinsic motivation. As, intrinsic motivation moderates between pro-social motivation and persistence, performance and productivity. Pro-social motivation can be conceptualizing in trait-like term and state-like term, as pro-social motivation reflects in the personality of a person (as a trait of sociability, nature of kindness and values of relations for others (Meglino & Korsgaard, 2004), and as psychological state of mind with pro-social attributes (it focuses on the protection and promotion of welfare of other people by contacting with them) (Batson, 1987; Grant, 2007). If we consider motivation for pro-social actions and egoistic actions, we can separate them by heuristic model on the continuum. Eisenberg et al., (2016) have elaborated both extremes and labelled them with different aspects of motivation. Pro-social motivation is considered as Sympathy/Empathic Concern based (motivated with goal of other's welfare e.g. justice and equality) and other side is egoistic (motivated with the goal of one's own benefit or welfare) is associated with many motives.

Transformational leadership has ability to infuse the roles of employees with meaningfulness but for all organizational settings it is not the same. As, public employees have to make positive change for society but it is not important for leaders in different settings to highlight its pro-social impact (Bellé, 2013). Some employees are aware of their job and the differences created by their tasks that they are adding some positive in the society. Transformational leaders take part in public sectors, where employees are not aware of their contribution to the society because in large organizations, it is hard to make connection of between organizational goals and output generated by them; therefore, it is not very effective that employees know about their inputs.

H₁: Visionary leadership is positively related to pro-social motivation.

2.3 Emotional Exhaustion

Mostly emotional exhaustion is fundamental to burnout occurrence (Maslach et al., 2001). It is important for organizations to avoid emotional exhaustion at workplace and it became dominant understanding in literature (Halbesleben & Demerouti, 2005; Kristensen et al., 2005; Measure et al., 2006). Particularly, banking sector deserves analysis for the increase in their stress and emotional exhaustion. International Labour Organization (2016) reported that disturbing matters for employees in banking and financial sector; included problem with the evaluation of workplace

efficiency, increase in the cases of violence and stress, excessive work load, time pressure, contradictory roles, and difficulties in customer relationship (Giga & Hoel, 2003) and another study by Wigert & Agrawal (2018) determined the causes of emotional exhaustion. So many researchers have studied job stress, job burnout, or job turnover, but they are incorporated in emotional exhaustion. As, Ahmad & Afgan (2016) have inspected the relationship between job stress and intention for job turnover with the job burnout incorporated as mediating variable. The result of this study revealed that relationship between burnout and turnover intention is significantly positive (greater the intensity of burnout, greater will be intent to resign) and relationship between job stress and job performance is significantly negative (as the level of stress will move up, performance of the employees will move down).

Chen et al., (2018) have studied the emotional exhaustion and passion of frontline employees, which revealed that frontline employee with harmonious passion use the deep acting strategy to face emotional labours and protect them from emotional exhaustion, while obsessively passionate frontline employee use surface acting strategy and result more emotional exhaustion.

It can be defined as the strength or too much energy required by an individual to fail or exhausted as burnout (Freudenberger, 1974), where burnout is physical and psychological state on which an individual get exhausted. The theory proposed by Maslach has three dimensions of burnout, and this study has chosen emotional exhaustion as common. These are explained as follow:

- Emotional Exhaustion (when individual exhaust his or her emotional energy resources, resultant by the extreme organizational demands and excessive workload.)
- Depersonalization (when an employee creates the isolation between him and customer and has no concern or sense of relationship to the customer.)
- Reduced Personal Accomplishment (when an individual fail to motivate itself for the job and completely attenuated the nous of competence and professional success.)

Emotional exhaustion is a disturbing psychological state which impairs the effect of motivational efforts of ethical leadership. The psychological empowerment of the leader directly influenced by emotional exhaustion and employees' potential for success indirectly influenced by emotional exhaustion (Dust et al., 2018; Javed et al., 2011). In Workplace magazine Wigert & Agrawal (2018) have concluded the five basic reason of emotional exhaustion (burnout), following Gallup study, they found 44% of employees sometimes feel burnout while 23% always feel burnout (Pendell, 2018). Those 5 causes of emotional exhaustion are given as follow:

- Unfair Treatment, Favouritism, Mistreatment at work by co-workers
- Unmanageable Workload
- Absence of Role Clarity
- Deficiency of communication and support from manager
- Undefined time pressure

H₂: Visionary leadership is negatively related to emotional exhaustion.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

From the above literature following framework is developed.

The research model of this study consists of one independent variable and two dependent variables. Visionary leadership is considered as independent variable while emotional exhaustion and pro-social motivation are dependent variables.

3. Methodology

In the field of research, one has to choose the appropriate methods or approaches to conduct the research, and theoretical systematic analysis of those methods or approaches is called methodology. Generally, it includes different concepts associated with branches of knowledge, as quantitative and qualitative techniques, paradigms, and theoretical models. It is important to explain that methodology doesn't useful to solve the problem or to find the solution, while it helps to understand the method or set of methods, or we can say best approach to solve the particular problem or find the solution.

3.1 Research Design

Research design is the part of methodology in which procedures of method is defined, which is used to measure the variables in research problem. It is the way to understand the nature of the research. *Techniques and Procedures (Questionnaire)* – Techniques and procedures includes the tools (questionnaires, questions of interview) and decisions employed with respect to philosophy of the study, approach and strategy used, choice, and time horizon in the final stage to have valid results.

3.2 Population and Sampling

Total population is not defined because most the banks were not willing to disclose any information regarding concerned branch. Therefore, we tried to make appropriate sample size of 370 employees from different Pakistani banks from Rawalpindi and Islamabad and distributed questionnaires, only 350 responded. It is considered it important to discuss the sample sizes of few studies, which have been conducted in banking sector of Pakistan as, Khan (2014) has collected data of 250 employees of banks from Rawalpindi/Islamabad, Ghalandari et al. (2012) has distributed 133 questionnaire, and Khattak et al. (2011) have collected data of 237 bank employees. While exceptionally, Haque & Aslam (2011) has collected data of 406 banking sector employees. These studies are mentioned to justify our sample size and respondents.

3.3 Instrument

Our instrument of data collection is questionnaire, because it is famous for research method, provide efficient and in expenses means of gathering large amount of information from different sample size this tool is effective for measuring subject behavior preferences opinion and attitude. which consist on 32 items (questions). There are three parts of questionnaire, one part for each variable. There are 6 items for visionary leadership, 8 items for pro-social motivation, 9 items for emotional exhaustion, and 9 items for bio data.

4. Data Analysis & Results

Data analysis is the systematic process to determine useful information for decision making from data by examining, purging, altering, and modelling the data sets. It is important for data to be reliable for analysis, therefore, have to test the reliability of data for each variable by using the software SPSS which is represented by the value of Cronbach's Alpha, and then the results of descriptive statistics. To compute the correlation and regression, first computed the means for every variable. Here, it is represented with variable as, 'VL' for 'Visionary Leadership', 'PSM' for 'Pro Social Motivation' and 'EE' for 'Emotional Exhaustion'.

4.1 Reliability

The meaning of reliability is trustworthy or performing consistently fit, while, in research reliability is refers to the reliability of tool or instrument used to assess information, which is expected to generate stable and consistent results. We used items of every variable to compute its reliability. Here, the measure of reliability is Cronbach's Alpha, and the values of Cronbach's Alphas are around 0.70 for every variable. It means that the instrument is reliable. Following results are showing the reliability of items.

Table 4.1: Outputs of Reliabilities

Reliability Statistics	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
<i>Visionary Leadership (VL)</i>	0.713	6
<i>Emotional Exhaustion (EE)</i>	0.695	9
<i>Pro Social Motivation (PSM)</i>	0.743	8

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics are the summarized representation of the given sample of the total population. In our results, it is representing the number of items, mean values and standard deviation of the data. Table 2 is showing the results of mean and standard deviation for each variable.

Mean of VL is 4.36, which is representing that most of the responses were around '4' (as in questionnaire) and 4 is supposed to be 'Agree'. Banks are also attributing with visionary leadership skills. Standard deviation is less than 1 (which is 0.83), which means responses were not so scattered. EE have mean value around '2' and 2 is supposed to be 'Disagree', so it can say that most employees in banks are not emotionally exhausted. Standard deviation of EE is 0.53, which less than the standard deviation of the VL. These results showed that bank employees are disagreeing on having emotional exhaustion. Mean value of PSM is 4.37 (it is also around '4'), which is also supposed to be 'Agree'. Here, we can say that banks employees have culture of pro-social motivation. The standard deviation is nearly 1 (which is 1.05). From the results of the descriptive statistics, concluded that banks have association with visionary leadership which is appealing low emotional exhaustion and high pro-social motivation.

Table: 4.2 – Results of Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Descriptive Statistics		No. of items
	Mean	Std. Deviation	
VL	4.3640	.82941	350
EE	2.1606	.52538	350
PSM	4.3654	1.05475	350

4.3 Correlation

It is the statistical relationship between variables. The results of correlation are showing that VL has significantly negative correlation with EE, (it is supporting H₂) and significantly positive

correlation with PSM (it is supporting H₁). It means that in banking sector, as the degree of visionary leadership will increase, degree of emotional exhaustion will be decrease. And, as the visionary leadership will increase then pro-social motivation will also be increase. Here, we'll ignore the correlation between EE and PSM because it is not the part of our model.

Table: 4.3 – Correlation Matrix

		VL	EE	PSM
Visionary Leadership (VL)	<i>Pearson_Correlation</i>	1	-0.453**	0.618**
	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>		0.000	0.000
	<i>N</i>	350	350	350
Emotional Exhaustion (EE)	<i>Pearson_Correlation</i>	-.453**	1	-0.392**
	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	.000		0.000
	<i>N</i>	350	350	350
Pro Social Motivation (PSM)	<i>Pearson_Correlation</i>	0.618**	-0.392**	1
	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	0.000	0.000	
	<i>N</i>	350	350	350

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.4 Regression Analysis

We have computed two regressions tests, between VL and EE, and VL and PSM. VL is our independent variable and EE and PSM are dependent variables, first, VL to EE and then VL to PSM shown as follow:

Regression from VL to PSM (H₁)

Regression analysis has three major result tables, known as model summary, ANOVA table, and regression coefficients, and they are given in table: 4.4, table: 4.5, and table: 4.6, respectively.

Table: 4.4– Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change
					F Change	df1	df2	
0.618	0.381	0.380	0.83073	0.381	214.610	1	348	0.000

The results of model summary are indicating positive correlation coefficient (R-square), it tells that 1 times change in VL will leads to 0.381 times change in PSM.

Table: 4.5 – ANOVA Table

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	<i>Regression</i>	148.105	1	148.105	214.610	0.000
	<i>Residual</i>	240.159	348	0.690		
	<i>Total</i>	388.264	349			

ANOVA table is showing F-Statistics is highly significant as F value is 148.10, it means we'll accept H₁ and conclude that visionary leadership is positively related to pro-social motivation.

Table: 4.6– Regression Coefficients and t-statistics

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	0.938	0.238		3.938	0.000
	VL_MEAN	0.785	0.054	0.618	14.65	0.000

Results of regression function (results are generated by SPSS) for first hypothesis 'H₁' revealed that there is a significantly positive relationship between VL and PSM, because the beta coefficient of VL is positive value, which is 0.785 and constant change of relationship is 0.938. The regression equation for this part of model is given as follow:

$$\text{Pro Social Motivation} = 0.938 + 0.785 (\text{Visionary Leadership}) + \text{Error Term}$$

Table: 4.7-Regression results from VL to EE (H₂)

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
					F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
0.453	0.205	0.203	0.46916	0.205	89.645	1	348	.000

4.5 Model Summary

The results of model summary are indicating positive correlation coefficient (R-square), it tells that 1 times change in VL will leads to 0.205 times change in EE.

Table: 4.8 – ANOVA Table

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	<i>Regression</i>	19.732	1	19.732	89.645	.000
	<i>Residual</i>	76.600	348	.220		
	<i>Total</i>	96.332	349			

ANOVA table is showing F-Statistics is highly significant as F value is 89.65, it means we'll accept H₂ and conclude that visionary leadership is negatively related to emotional exhaustion.

Table: 4.9 – Regression Coefficients and t-statistics

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
		1	<i>(Constant)</i>	3.412			0.134	
	<i>VL</i>	-0.287	0.030	-0.453	-9.468	0.000	-0.346	-0.227

Results of regression function (results are generated by SPSS) for second hypothesis 'H₂' revealed that there is a significantly negative relationship between VL and EE, because the beta coefficient of VL is negative value, which is – 0.287 and constant change of relationship is 3.41. The regression equation for this part of model is given as follow:

$$\text{Emotional Exhaustion} = 3.412 - 0.287 (\text{Visionary Leadership}) + \text{Error Term}$$

5. Discussion

The current study endeavoured to examine the effect of visionary leadership on the enhancement of pro-social motivation and attenuation of the emotional exhaustion in banking sector

of Pakistan. Two objectives and two corresponding hypotheses (H_1 and H_2) and tested them by regression analysis. All the empirical results were in the favour of set objectives and hypotheses has accepted by regression analysis. We have conducted four tests, first was reliability test (value of Cronbach's Alpha), second was descriptive statistics, third was correlation metrics, and the last was regression analysis. First objective was achieved when correlation between VL and PSM came positive and proved the positive relationship between them. And, second objective was come true, when correlation between VL and EE was negative value which proved the negative relationship. Regression analysis was solely used to test our hypotheses (H_1 and H_2), where H_1 was tested to examine the nature of relationship (positive or negative) from visionary leadership to pro-social motivation.

As, positive relationship was observed from correlation metrics, and the result came as per expectation. The value of beta coefficient (β) also turned out to be positive and p-value was too small, which are showing that VL has significantly positive effect on PSM. Therefore, concluded that visionary leadership is very useful to foster the pro-social motivation in banks. Here, if we only consider the results of descriptive statistics to assess the current situation in banks, results are showing that employees of banks are agree on presence of visionary leadership in their organizations. It means that banks employees find visionary skills in their management. And results regarding PSM are also demonstrating that responses of banks employees are supporting the existence of PSM culture.

Second objective was realized when correlation between VL and EE came negative and proved the negative relationship between them. Regression analysis was solely used to test our hypotheses (H_1 and H_2), H_2 was tested to examine the nature of relationship (positive or negative) from visionary leadership to emotional exhaustion. As, negative relationship was observed from correlation metrics, it was expected that this relationship will be negative and the results turned out as expectations. The value of beta coefficient (β) was negative and p-value was too small, which are showing that VL has significantly negative effect on EE. Therefore, we can conclude that visionary leadership is very useful to reduce the emotional exhaustion in banks. Here, if we only consider the results of descriptive statistics to assess the current situation of emotional exhaustion in banks, they are showing that employees of banks are disagree on presence of emotional exhaustion in their organizations.

5.1 Conclusion

First objective was achieved when correlation between VL and PSM came positive and proved the positive relationship between them. And, second objective was come true, when correlation between VL and EE was negative value which proved the negative relationship. The value of beta coefficient (β) was positive, and p-value was too small, which are showing that VL has significantly positive effect on PSM. Therefore, concluded that visionary leadership is very

useful to foster the pro-social motivation in banks. The value of beta coefficient (β) was negative, and p-value was too small, which are showing that VL has significantly negative effect on EE. Therefore, concluded that visionary leadership is very useful to reduce the emotional exhaustion in banks.

5.2 Suggestions

The model of our study is simple without any mediating variable or moderating variable in model. As, for further research, there are options to use moderator or mediator between visionary leadership and emotional exhaustion. Further, this model can be examined in the perspective of hospitals, the nursing staff of hospital can be population for this model. Future studies could investigate the motivational variables (intrinsic motivation, goal setting motivation etc.), effective variables (job satisfaction), and behavioural variables (contextual performance, extra efforts) with influence of visionary leadership or its interaction with them.

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